

Supporting information

Model limitations

To enable projections of vegetation dynamics under future environmental conditions at a large scale (particularly in the absence of extensive financial funds), computational models usually represent the most applicable tool for the task since they can simulate over large spatial extents at a comparably small investment of time and resources. Nevertheless, both model inputs as well as model processes may bear uncertainties, among others in the form of inherent assumptions on environmental or physiological processes (i.e. parametrization), bias or measurement errors (e.g., climate inputs, remote-sensing data) or scale mismatches (Fisher et al., 2010; Nishina et al., 2015; Zaehle et al., 2005). Although the here used DGVM has been validated against observational data in many previous studies, the assumed ecological relationships may not be constant under a future climate. Positively, compared with earlier studies covering the study region (e.g., Snell et al., 2013) our study accounts for nitrogen limitation and topographic heterogeneity. On the other hand, for influencing factors like CO₂ fertilization or disturbances uncertainties persist. Furthermore, although general climate trends are largely kept throughout data down-scaling, site conditions may vary at a small scale. Particularly precipitation projections are coupled to high uncertainties and were hence kept at the resolution of 0.5° of the original bias-corrected ISIMIP dataset. While these uncertainties are also influenced by the choice of socio-economic and emission pathways, this study set its aim to cover a broad spectrum of plausible emission pathways and thus provides a range of results. Lastly, it should be noted, that our approach only estimated pressures and not actual transformations of ecosystems. Accordingly, actual impacts may vary based on multiple factors like land use intensity, ecosystem resilience or other disturbances such as wind, fire or pest outbreaks, all of which represent important current research avenues.

Table S1: Biomization scheme.

Biome	Conditions^a
Tropical Broadleaved Evergreen Forest	Total LAI > 2.5 <i>and</i> TrBE LAI ≥ 66% Total LAI
Tropical Seasonal Forest	Total LAI > 2.5 <i>and</i> TrBE LAI ≥ 33% Total LAI <i>and</i> TrBR LAI ≥ 33% Total LAI
Tropical Dry Forest	Total LAI > 2.5 <i>and</i> TrBR LAI ≥ 66% Total LAI
Tropical Montane Forest	Total LAI > 2.5 <i>and</i> TeBE LAI > 10% Total LAI <i>and</i> TeNE LAI < 25% Total LAI <i>and</i> Number of dry months ^b < 5
Seasonally Dry Montane Forest (pine-oak)	Total LAI > 2.5 <i>and</i> TeBE LAI > 10% Total LAI <i>and</i> Number of dry months ≥ 5
Savanna	Total LAI > 1.5 <i>and</i> (Grass NPP / Tree NPP) < 1.8 <i>and</i> C4 LAI > C3 LAI
Grassland	Total LAI > 1.5 <i>and</i> (Grass NPP / Tree NPP) > 1.8 <i>and</i> C4 LAI > C3 LAI <i>or</i> Total LAI > 3.0 <i>and</i> C3 LAI ≥ 66% Total LAI
Desert	Total LAI < 0.2

^a Abbreviations: LAI = Leaf area index, NPP = net primary production, TrBE = Tropical broadleaved evergreen forest, TrBR = Tropical broadleaved raingreen forest, TeBE = Temperate broadleaved evergreen forest, TeNE = Temperate needleleaved evergreen forest, C4 = C4 grass, C3 = C3 grass

^b Dry months are defined as months with <100 mm precipitation.

Figure S2: PFT shares based on foliar projective cover in intact forest landscapes over different future time periods.

Pressure factors 2071-2100 (unprotected KBA highlighted)

Figure S3: Continuous pressure scores for unprotected KBA in Central America for the time period 2071-2100.

Pressure factors 2071-2100

Figure S4: Continuous pressure scores for the whole Central American region for the time period 2071-2100.

Figure S5: Comparison of LPJ-GUESS outputs (average over all runs) with satellite-derived products (MODIS-NPP) and biome maps (Olson et al. 2001). Edited from Baumbach et al. (under review).

Figure S6: Average yearly climate input data (tas = temperature average surface, pr = precipitation) for the Central American region under different scenarios (piControl = pre-industrial emission levels, W5E5v2.0 = observational dataset for comparison). Edited from ISIMIP Data Team 2022.

Supplementary references

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